

Addendum to SGLT2 analysis plan. V1.1

The original analysis plan is uploaded to Zenodo as v1.0. This is an addition to this plan.

Analysis of a non-trial broad population:

In addition to the analysis in v1.0 we will pursue the same analysis in a broad non-trial population with the aim of investigating the same endpoints (continuous usage of glargine compared to degludec). The population in question is as follows:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria
Individuals over or equal to 40 years of age and less than 90 years of age will be included
Individuals on SGLT2i or DPP4i must have redeemed a prescription for metformin during the last 10 years
There must be an Hba1c level present at baseline (1 year prior to index) and it must be over 48 mmol/mol
The presence of any CVD criteria as mentioned in the trial emulation results in exclusion. Diagnosis codes present in table 2. (1,3,4,5,10,11,12)
A eGFR of less than 30 ml/min measured within 2 years from baseline results in exclusion
Patients who immigrated into the country less than 10 years prior to baseline are excluded.

The main outcome will be investigated in subgroups of sociodemographic factors such as sex, age, income, and education, as well as disease markers such as diabetes duration and HbA1c.